

Effect of Metal- β -Diketonates in Polymer Degradation

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The effects of ferric- β -diketonates on the degradation of polystyrene were studied by using, viscometry, ultraviolet and visible spectroscopy and oxygen absorption measurements. The spectra of $\text{Fe}(\text{DPM})_3$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{ac ac})_3$ were considerably changed in the presence of polystyrene. A four fold decrease in viscosity of polystyrene solution was observed in the presence of $\text{Fe}(\text{DPM})_3$. The probable course of reaction was assumed to be first the formation of a π -complex between the polymer and chelates and subsequent decomposition to give free radicals, which bring about degradation.

RESULTS on the auto-oxidative decomposition of transition metal- β -diketonates suggested the possibility of these chelates acting as initiators for the radical polymerisation of vinyl monomers¹. Research in this field revealed the importance of both central metal atom as well as the ligand structure^{2,3}. Metal acetyl acetonates as initiators for vinyl polymerisation constitute a well explored field⁴. Ferric dipivaloyl methide $\text{Fe}(\text{DPM})_3$ and ferric-acetyl acetonate $\text{Fe}(\text{ac ac})_3$ are known to initiate vinyl polymerisation. Also there exist conclusive evidences indicating the involvement of the monomer in the initiation step of the polymerisation reaction⁵⁻⁷. Initiation involves the formation of a π -type complex between the monomer and the chelate and its subsequent decomposition to free radicals brings about polymerisation⁴⁻⁷. In this communication, we would like to report the role of ferric- β -diketonates in the degradation of vinyl polymers like polystyrene (PS). Degradable polymers are having great interest in the disposability of waste plastic materials.

Ultraviolet and visible spectral measurements were made using a Beckman Model 25 Spectrophotometer. Oxygen absorption measurements were carried out in a set up similar to that devised by Hammond and others⁸. Viscosity measurements were carried out in a Ubbelohde Viscometer. A.R. quality acetyl acetone and dipivaloyl-methane supplied respectively by E. Merck, Germany and Aldrich Chemical Company, Wisconsin, U.S.A. were used directly without further purification. $\text{Fe}(\text{DPM})_3$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{ac ac})_3$ were prepared according to the methods of Hammond et al and Urbain and Debierne^{9,10} respectively. Azo-bis-isobutyronitrile (AIBN) was a product of E. Merck and recrystallised thrice before use. Monomers were supplied by British Drug House, England and High Purity Chemicals, New Delhi. Analar grade solvents were used for polymerisation and subsequent precipitation. Solvents were distilled twice and purified according to the methods described by Riddick and Bunger¹¹. Styrene was freed from added inhibitors by washing with 5% sodium hydroxide solution

followed by repeated washing with distilled water. The monomer was kept overnight over fused CaCl_2 , filtered and distilled under vacuum in an all glass apparatus just before use. The middle fraction was used for polymerisation.

Polystyrene was prepared using standard procedure of polymerising both in the presence of AIBN as well as thermally. They were purified by the usual procedure of repeated precipitation and finally dried under vacuum. The polymer was dissolved in dioxane and varying amounts of $\text{Fe}(\text{DPM})_3$ or $\text{Fe}(\text{ac ac})_3$ were added, and their spectra (U.V. and visible), viscosity and rate of oxidation were followed.

Oxygen uptake by polystyrene was measured in a modified apparatus to that described by Hammond et al both in the absence and in the presence of $\text{Fe}(\text{DPM})_3$ or $\text{Fe}(\text{ac ac})_3$ at 60°. The rate of oxidation of polystyrene in the presence of AIBN was found to be enhanced considerably on addition of the ferric chelates. The rate of oxidation increased with increase in the concentration of the ferric chelates. A typical set of results with $\text{Fe}(\text{DPM})_3$ are presented in Fig. 1. Similar trends were noticed in the case of $\text{Fe}(\text{ac ac})_3$ also. After the oxygen uptake measurement was over the polymer was precipitated by methanol containing 0.1 M aqueous NaF. The filtrate was concentrated in vacuum and the pH adjusted to 3.5 by acetate buffer and 0.25% aqueous solution of phenanthroline was added. The development of red colour indicated the presence of ferrous ion in the reaction mixture.

Considering the general scheme of free radical oxidation one can briefly summarise the reaction steps as :

Fig. 1. Effect of $\text{Fe}(\text{DPM})_3$ on the oxidation of polystyrene at 60°C .
 (i) Polystyrene (20% by wt. in dioxane) and AIBN ($1 \times 10^{-4}M$).
 (ii) Polystyrene (20% by wt. in dioxane), AIBN ($1 \times 10^{-4}M$) and $\text{Fe}(\text{DPM})_3$ ($1 \times 10^{-6}M$).
 (iii) Polystyrene (20% by wt. in dioxane), AIBN ($1 \times 10^{-4}M$) and $\text{Fe}(\text{DPM})_3$ ($1 \times 10^{-6}M$).

Fig. 2. Effect of Polystyrene on the visible spectra of $\text{Fe}(\text{DPM})_3$.
 (i) Concentration $\text{Fe}(\text{DPM})_3 = 8.390 \times 10^{-4}M$ in dioxane alone.
 (ii) $\text{Fe}(\text{DPM})_3$ with polystyrene. Concn. of polystyrene 20% by wt. in dioxane. Concn. of $\text{Fe}(\text{DPM})_3 = 8.390 \times 10^{-4}M$.

That the oxidation of polystyrene in the present system is free radical in nature was indicated by the fact that presence of hydroquinone inhibited the

oxidation. The production of radicals R^\cdot to accelerate the oxidation reaction was thought to be due to the decomposition of the complex formed between the polystyrene and the ferric chelate resulting in the production of free radical R^\cdot and $\text{Fe}(\text{DPM})_2$ as evidenced by the phenanthroline reaction.

The formation of such a complex was supported by the spectral data (Fig. 2). The spectra of $\text{Fe}(\text{DPM})_3$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{ac ac})_3$ were considerably changed in the presence of polystyrene (both U.V. and visible). The visible spectra of $\text{Fe}(\text{DPM})_3$ was shifted from 560 nm to 527 nm (λ_{max}) indicating a shift of 33 nm. In the case of $\text{Fe}(\text{ac ac})_3$ λ_{max} shifted by 32 nm.

Viscosity of polystyrene changed by about 4 fold in the presence of $\text{Fe}(\text{DPM})_3$ and a typical case is presented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Effect of $\text{Fe}(\text{DPM})_3$ on the Intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ of Polystyrene with time.
 Polystyrene (20% by wt. in dioxane)
 AIBN ($1 \times 10^{-4}M$) and $\text{Fe}(\text{DPM})_3$ ($1 \times 10^{-6}M$).

It is now known for certain that these ferric chelates do not yield radicals through direct homolytic fission^{6,7}. This is also supported by the fact these chelates fail to absorb oxygen by themselves after keeping for over 6 hours at 70° . Hence the probable course of reaction might be brought about by the formation of a π -complex between the polymer and the chelates as evidenced from spectral data. This complex in turn decomposes to give free radicals leading to the oxidative degradation.

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